

THE IMPORTANCE OF AGRO-INDUSTRY IN THE ECONOMY

Mamayusupova Shakhina Ulugbek qizi

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti

shahinamamayusupova28@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The growth of agriculture in the world economy in the next years is increasing sharply. That is why it is a product of agriculture land, water and labor resources, which are the main factors of production. Agriculture has developed and is developing its own characteristics. It is shown in the article that studying at the level of agriculture is significant.

Key words: *Organization, labour resources, agriculture, process, livestock, technology.*

Production in the agricultural sector is largely dependent on land. Relations related to ownership, management and use of land are called agrarian relations. One of the important features of reproduction in agriculture is that the production process here is directly related to living beings - land, plants, livestock, and natural laws are connected with economic laws. Land participates in this as a tool of labor and a subject of labor. Earth differs from other means of production in that it does not corrode or wear out during its use. On the contrary, if it is used correctly, its productivity will increase.

Healthy, sustainable and inclusive food systems are critical to achieve the world's development goals. Agricultural development is one of the most powerful tools to end extreme poverty, boost shared prosperity, and feed a projected 9.7 billion people by 2050. Growth in the agriculture sector is two to four times more effective in raising incomes among the poorest compared to other sectors. Agriculture is also crucial to economic growth: accounting for 4% of global gross domestic

product (GDP) and in some least developing countries, it can account for more than 25% of GDP.¹

Apart from this, the growth of agriculture in the world economy in the next years is increasing sharply. That is why it is a product of agriculture land, water, and labor resources, which are the main factors of production.

Agriculture has developed and is developing its own characteristics. It is shown in the article that studying at the level of agriculture is significant. Agriculture is an integral part of the world's economy, mainly for developing countries. It is the primary source of employment, income, and food, and these basic needs fulfilled by agriculture all over the world. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the share of the agricultural population is 67% of the total population. It recorded 39.4% of the GDP and in that 43% of all exports includes agriculture commodities. We are here with this blog to show all the information about top agricultural producing countries in the world, stay tuned.²

Delivery of food products for the agricultural population in addition to industrial sectors (food, soft feed, textiles, chili, medicine, perfume industry, etc.) as raw materials, horse hunting (horse breeding, camel breeding, etc.). Farming industries (grain growing, cotton growing, vegetable growing, fruit growing, viticulture, etc.) and livestock industries (cattle breeding, pig farming, sheep farming, poultry farming, cocoon farming, fishing, etc.) includes. It is simple to develop this network together allows the correct use of labor resources.

The systematic modernization of industrial sectors in the country and the introduction of new technologies into production, the organization of production chains of finished products with high added value through deep processing of raw materials will ensure the competitiveness of the economy. For example, countries such as Japan, South Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Hong Kong and China have achieved an "economic miracle" by specializing in the export of finished products with high added value.

¹ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/agriculture/overview>

² <https://www.tractorjunction.com/blog/top-10-agricultural-producing-countries-in-the-world/>

Share Graph of Agricultural Production in the World Economy¹

Above we can see that proportion of agricultural production all the world. Agricultural products are quite less compared to other products but in 2018 this statistics below shows just below at 2000. World experience shows that the profitability of capital or labor spent on production related to resources and raw materials decreases over time. That is, in order to increase economic growth and production in countries specializing in the supply of raw materials, first of all, it is necessary to increase the costs of creating new production facilities. Also, the economies of countries specializing in the supply of raw materials are highly dependent on foreign markets, and adverse changes in foreign markets lead to a weakening of the country's economy. Based on the above, the issue of creating a competitive finished product production chain with high added value through deep processing of raw materials in the republic and increasing the share of finished products in the export composition by directing these products to export is considered urgent.

¹ https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Share-Graph-of-Agricultural-Production-in-the-World-Economy-62_fig1_342437214

FIGURE 11.
SHARE OF AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING EMPLOYMENT IN TOTAL
EMPLOYMENT BY REGION

Source: ILO Modelled Estimates, ILOSTAT

Statistical yearbook world food and agriculture in 20211

So, in this picture we can understand that year by year our agriculture employment in total employment by region decreasing because of improving technologies as well. But it is really necessary to improve of agriculturer path in all countires. It causes a big amount of global improvement of economy situation.

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